

METHODS OF TEACHING "COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY" IN THE DEVELOPED COUNTRIES OF THE WORLD

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we can see that the concept of information technology is very active today. At the same time, our time is the age of information technology, and the developing IT industry is talking about its teaching methods, as well as the role of programming languages in their teaching and in foreign countries.

We know that the concept of information technology is becoming more and more popular every year, because it is the age of modern technology. It is a department that studies the laws of teaching the basics of computer science and computer engineering, computer science and information technology in schools, academic lyceums and professional colleges. The purpose of teaching computer science is: To equip future teachers with knowledge, skills and abilities to creatively teach computer science and apply new pedagogical and information technologies in their practical activities;

To prepare future teachers for the organization and conduct of various forms of classroom and extracurricular activities in the field of computer science;

Develop and deepen the understanding of future teachers about the ways and great

prospects of informing the field of education. The future teacher of computer science will teach the younger generation the importance of the subjects "Fundamentals of Computer Science and Computer Engineering", "Computer Science" and "Information Technology" taught in secondary schools, academic lyceums and professional colleges, the principles of their content. , as well as understand their relationship to other disciplines. [1] The interest in this field is growing year by year, and the term is becoming more and more important in the world's most developed countries, which have the greatest influence on it. In addition, a lot of work is being done in this area in our country. Information technology is now what everyone calls IT in modern parlance. The term is synonymous with computer science. First of all, we can say below what

information technology is, where it is produced and how it relates to science.

Information technology is the technology of data management and processing. Usually this term is understood as computer technology. In the field of information technology, work is carried out on the collection, storage, protection, processing and transmission of various information through computers and computer networks. The main technical means of information technology are non-organizational means of communication - telephone, teletype, telefax, etc.

Although information technology has existed at various stages of human development, a distinctive feature of modern information society is that, for the first time in the history of civilization, the power expended on knowledge, production, energy, raw materials, materials and consumables that is, information technology is at the forefront of existing new technologies. [2] If we compare the level of IT technologies in the world and the methods of teaching them, such as the media, with our country, we can see it clearly in the example of Europe. In foreign countries, IT technology is now a leader in all areas, as the efficiency of the Internet continues to grow from year to year, and revenues from social networks and businesses will drive the development of IT. Also, when it comes to their teaching methods, in Europe, every student has to develop a new project that will benefit the public and the future. This, of course, requires a lot of effort and attention.

When teaching them about information technology, they first learn about the term in detail, first small things and then big things. Anyone who wants to study information technology should be aware of

every field. If you want to be a strong programmer, English is also important for learning computer science, mathematics, and programming languages. We cannot call such disciplines programmers if they do not know programming. Nowadays in IT it is necessary to know programming languages like Html / python programming / Pascal.

Python ([ˈpʌɪθ (ə) n] – payton, python) is a high-level general-purpose programming language for various fields. His design philosophy emphasizes code reading using significant digression. Its language constructs and object-oriented approach help programmers write clear, logical code for small and large projects. [3] Python is also the language of artificial intelligence and data engineering.

Python can run on almost any platform, especially Windows, Linux, Mac OS X, Palm OS, Mac OS, and more. Python also has a written implementation for the Microsoft.NET platform, called the IronPython programming environment.

HTML is the HyperText Markup Language, or HTML, the default markup language for documents to display in a web browser. This can be helped by technologies such as Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) and scripting languages such as JavaScript. [4] Web browsers retrieve HTML documents from a web server or local memory and display the documents on multimedia web pages. HTML semantically describes the structure of a web page and initially contains signals for the appearance of the document.

HTML elements are the building blocks of HTML pages. With HTML constructions, other objects, such as images and interactive forms, can be inserted into the specified page. HTML provides a tool for creating structured documents by defining

the structural semantics of text, such as headings, paragraphs, lists, links, quotations, and other elements. [5]

There is a lot of work being done in this area in almost all countries today, and there is a

lot of news, and it is clear that teaching such information technology is a complex and responsible profession. Teachers teach this field to young people through various methodological methods.

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